

The Important Role of Literacy in Increasing the Potential of Indonesian Students and Students

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ABSTRACT

To support this, the Ministry of Education and Culture developed the Literacy Movement in Schools (GLS). GLS aims to foster a culture of reading, GLS, writing, listening, speaking. (literacy), and selecting information from school members, both principals, students and teachers, which leads to the ability to understand information critically and reflectively. These skills are very necessary in creating creative-productive learning. The theoretical and empirical results of the study show that literacy has a significant role in productive creative learning. These roles include (1) the literacy movement in schools is able to develop critical thinking skills which are very necessary in implementing creative-productive learning, (2) literacy skills are needed in exploratory activities in creative-productive learning, namely by reading, writing, sorting information to solve problems. and discovering new concepts, (3) literacy skills will empower students to conduct exploration, conduct observations, interviews, conduct experiments, and be wise in sorting information from various sources thereby increasing the effectiveness of implementing creative-productive learning in schools.

INTRODUCTION

Talking about literacy, there needs to be self-awareness to understand the meaning of the meaning of literacy, why not because most people only read and know the meaning and purpose of what they read but do not apply it in action, for example a poster "it is forbidden to throw rubbish here" they know the meaning and aim but not implementing it so I feel that this literacy has not been implemented well. The term literacy generally refers to a series of individual abilities and skills in reading, writing, speaking, calculating and solving problems at a certain level of expertise that is needed in everyday life, so we as title developers as students need to understand the meaning of literacy because by strong literacy, we are able to master all forms of things well, such as effective communication skills. Literacy is also a very important skill and must be possessed by every community for everyday life. As the importance of the educational process depends on literacy ability and awareness.

In 2015 the Indonesian Ministry of Education and Culture issued a regulation Minister No. 23 of 2015. This Ministerial Regulation contains the development of character which includes the School Literacy Movement (GLS) by requiring students to read non-learning books for 10-15 minutes before learning begins. This movement aims for students to have a reading culture and writing to create lifelong learning. This is done because basically reading and writing skills require practice and learning habits.

With this literacy having a real role in everyday life, here are some of the roles of literacy:

- Strengthen personality values by reading and writing
- Can develop character
- Can provide critical assessments
- Develop and foster a culture of literacy
- Can increase knowledge and understanding

At some point, we as students have felt that sometimes we accidentally use our free time for things that are not useful, so from now on let's use it for things that are useful. One way is to read books. Because "Reading is a window to the world" are words that we may often hear or have known. It is true that reading is a window to the world. Because by reading, we will get various benefits, increasing in terms of health and knowledge so that it is useful in increasing our competence as students and is expected to provide a breath of fresh air in increasing our knowledge and productivity as effective and efficient students.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

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METHODOLOGY

The research method that we use in this writing uses the literature review method. The literature review step consists of several methods that will be used, namely selecting the topic to be reviewed, searching and selecting articles related to the topic to be researched, analyzing and synthesizing the literature and organizing the writing. Our focus in this research consists of reviewing literature regarding the role of literacy towards pupils and students from various points of view and theories. The focus of another study or which will be related to our research sources is the role of teachers or supervisors in dealing with the problem of minimal literacy for students. By focusing on the two results of this research topic it will point to the important role of literacy for self-development for students and college students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Literacy is a person's ability to use potential and skills in processing and understanding information when carrying out reading and writing activities. Through literacy skills, a person not only gains knowledge but can also use his knowledge and experience as a reference in the future. Critical thinking is an intellectual thinking process in which the thinker deliberately assesses the quality of making decisions when using all these skills effectively in the right context and type. In his thinking, thinking uses reflective, independent, clear and rational thinking. With good literacy skills, it is hoped that critical thinking skills will increase. Critical thinking ability is a thought process that can be accepted by reflective reasoning which is directed at deciding what to do or believe, in this case not haphazardly, not leading to just any conclusion but to the best conclusion. Therefore, by increasing literacy in everyday life, we can overcome current problems by getting sources of information from various platforms, both virtual and real. And it is hoped that by increasing literacy we will be able to think broadly and increase sources of experience from reading and researching useful literacy sources to increase opportunities to increase knowledge and insight that play a role for ourselves and the future.

The role of literacy according to the following experts:

1. According to Elizabeth Sulzby "1986", Literacy is the language skills possessed by a person in communicating "reading, speaking, listening and writing" in different ways according to their goals. If defined briefly, the definition of literacy is the ability to write and read.

2. According to Harvey J. Graff "2006", Literacy is a person's ability to write and read.
3. According to Jack Goody, literacy is a person's ability to read and write.
4. According to the Merriam-Webster online dictionary, literacy is the ability or quality of literacy in a person, which includes the ability to read, write and also recognize and understand ideas visually.
5. According to UNESCO "The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization", Literacy is a set of real skills, especially skills in reading and writing which are independent of the context in which the skills are acquired and who acquires them.
6. According to Alberta, literacy is the ability to read and write, increase knowledge and skills, think critically in solving problems, and the ability to communicate effectively which can develop potential and participate in community life.
7. The National Institute for Literacy, defines literacy as "an individual's ability to read, write, speak, calculate and solve problems at the skill level required for work, family and society." This definition interprets literacy from a more contextual perspective. This definition implies that the definition of literacy depends on the skills needed in a particular environment.
8. The Education Development Center (EDC) states that literacy is more than just the ability to read and write. But more than that, literacy is an individual's ability to use all the potential and skills they have in their life. With the understanding that literacy includes the ability to read words and read the world

Definition of Literacy Role Strategy

In general, literacy role strategies are strategies used in learning to build students' understanding, writing skills, writing skills and effective communication skills (Suharsimi Arikunto). Literacy strategies can also be used in mathematics learning in the industrial era 4.0 (Dr. HM Thamrin Abdullah). Literacy itself is a person's ability to process and understand information when carrying out the reading and writing process (according to the KBBI). The definition of literacy always evolves according to the challenges of the times, and currently the term literacy has begun to be used in a broader sense.

First: Aspects of Strength/Potential for individuals

The strategy for training the brain by reading books is very good as a brain and mind exercise. Reading can help keep the brain so that it always carries out its functions perfectly. When reading, the brain is required to think, analyze various problems, look for solutions and solutions and discover new things. These activities can make people smarter because their brain cells continue to maximize their potential and are not allowed to fall asleep in a long sleep. Strategies for Having a Good Level of Concentration with people who read books usually have the ability to make decisions quickly and correctly. Reading books makes our brain focus and concentrate. This helps us develop objectivity skills. A strategy to develop writing skills. If your job requires you to

write a lot, such as a journalist, public relations person, or even a musician, reading books is highly recommended. A well-written book can be an inspiration for you in composing beautiful and interesting words. A strategy to provide calm is very possible if the body relaxes when reading a book. Research has proven that reading spiritual books can lower blood pressure and calm the heart. Strategies for building self-confidence the more we read, the more knowledge we gain. As knowledge increases, self-confidence will increase. So, this is a chain reaction. Because we are good readers, people will look to us for answers. Our feelings towards ourselves will get better. A strategy to increase the discipline of finding time to read is something that needs to be done to increase understanding and knowledge from various sources of information, whether from books, articles, journals and applications.

Second: Health aspects for yourself

Strategies to Increase Brain Ability Fiction books usually have interesting storylines and are not boring. Fiction stories provoke readers to imagine existing characters with different perceptions. This process is what makes our brains work so that we can amazingly remember all the story plots from hundreds of pages. This is a good exercise for our brain. Of course, the results will be maximum if done regularly. Strategies to prevent Alzheimer's disease, researchers found the growth of brain cells in people who often read books. The brain's binding capacity will also increase if trained regularly. Not only reading books, activities such as completing crossword puzzles or playing Sudoku can also prevent memory loss and prevent Alzheimer's disease. Strategies for having good analytical skills When reading fiction books, have we ever heard ourselves say, "I think we know end of this story,". If yes, then that is a sign that our analytical skills are working. If our predictions are often correct, then our brain is working well. Strategies to relieve stress no matter how heavy the routine is, such as work load or relationship problems with your partner, a series of beautiful words can provoke the brain to relax. A beautifully written novel or fiction story can provoke the brain to forget about existing burdens for a moment so that our stress can be reduced. A strategy for developing a healthy sleep pattern is if we get into the habit of reading a book before going to bed, then it acts as an alarm for the body and sends a signal that it has it's time to go to sleep. This will help you get a restful sleep and wake up refreshed in the morning..

Third: Aspects of knowledge for knowledge

Reading will increase vocabulary. We can learn how to guess the meaning of a word (which we don't yet know) by reading the context of other words in a sentence. Books, especially challenging ones, will show us many words that we may not yet know. Adding insight and knowledge when we read books, specifically textbooks, we can increase our insight and knowledge. Because, textbooks contain the knowledge we need. Knowing the most up-to-date information, it is not uncommon for books to contain various information, for example magazines. By reading magazines, we find out the most updated

information. Because magazines contain a lot of information including product prices, competitions and so on. To get new motivation, currently there are many biographical books of successful people. So, if we read a biography of a successful person, we can be motivated to achieve our goals. Because the book contains about the person's life journey and struggle to become successful.

Fourth: Entertainment function at the right time

Reducing boredom if we feel bored, we will feel better by reading a good book, right? If we want to break the monotonous feeling of laziness and boring uncreative life, then go and pick up an interesting book, open the pages and explore a new world full of information and intelligence. As a medium of entertainment besides educational books, magazines, textbooks biographies, many entertainment books such as comics and novels are also produced. Usually this book contains fictional stories. So, we can read this book in our free time, so we can feel more entertained. Apart from getting entertainment, we can also get new insights from our reading sources.

The Importance of the Role of Mentors in Handling Literacy Problems for Students

The important objectives of the supervisor's role in dealing with literacy problems for students are as follows:

1. Increase literacy awareness: Advisors are responsible for providing students with a better understanding of the importance of literacy. They can help teach the importance of reading, writing, and understanding relevant information. Thus, students will have a higher awareness of the importance of literacy in their lives.
2. Provide personal guidance: Tutors can provide personal guidance to students in developing their literacy skills. They can provide guidance and exercises appropriate to the student's ability level. With this personal guidance, students can be more focused and supported in overcoming the literacy difficulties they face.
3. Encourage reading habits: Tutors can inspire and encourage students to read regularly. By providing suggestions regarding interesting and relevant books, and introducing students to various genres of literature, supervisors can help increase students' interest and reading habits. This will help students broaden their horizons, develop their imagination and improve their language skills.
4. Providing literacy resources: Advisors are also responsible for providing the literacy resources needed by students. This may include access to libraries, books, magazines, or digital platforms that provide literacy materials. Coaches can help students identify relevant resources and assist them in making good use of them.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conclusion that we can form from the results of this research is that literacy plays an important role for each individual in everyday life so that our source of knowledge continues to operate even in free time. Therefore, we as

mentors, students and students must maintain our literacy so that our insight and perspective remains broad and bad and critical thinking does not occur regarding the problems that occur on this earth. Teachers can use varied methods in implementing learning at school so that students do not feel bored during the learning process and parents and guardians can monitor their children at home during the learning process so that when they need guidance they can ask their guardians. Therefore, teachers and parents and guardians of students must provide support and motivation for them to maintain their literacy.

FURTHER STUDY

Every research is subject to limitations; thus, you can explain them here and briefly suggest further investigations.

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